

The problem with two balls

Harald Schröder

We look at the following figure:

Let the large ball represent the earth, as an example. Now we want to calculate the radius r of the small ball. The angle of appearance α , the distance b on the earth's surface and the earth's radius R are known.

1

Very simple is the case $r \ll R$, then it is $b \ll R$ and we can recognize simply with the rectangular kite:

$$r \approx b \cdot \tan \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

Now we turn to the case that r is not negligibly small compared to the earth's radius R . We view the following figure:

This 4-gon **cannot** be constructed. Only 4 quantities are known. r and x remain unknown. The angle β can be determined with $\beta = \frac{b}{R}$. Then we have β in circular measure. We calculate the angle γ with:

$$\gamma = 360^\circ - \alpha - 90^\circ - 90^\circ - \beta = 180^\circ - \alpha - \beta$$

We use the cosine law twice to the drawn diagonals:

$$(1) \quad r^2 + (r+R)^2 - 2r \cdot (r+R) \cdot \cos(180^\circ - \alpha - \beta) = R^2 + x^2 - 2Rx \cdot \cos(90^\circ + \alpha)$$

2

$$(2) \quad x^2 + r^2 = R^2 + (r + R)^2 - 2R \cdot (r + R) \cdot \cos \beta$$

Solving from equation (2) to x^2 :

$$x^2 = 2R^2 + 2rR - 2R^2 \cos \beta - 2rR \cos \beta = 2R^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) + 2rR \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)$$

Finally:

$$x^2 = 2 \cdot (R^2 + rR) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)$$

Insertion in equation (1) yields:

$$r^2 + R^2 + 2rR + r^2 - (2Rr + 2r^2) \cdot \cos(180^\circ - \alpha - \beta)$$

$$= R^2 + 2 \cdot (R^2 + rR) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) - 2R \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot (R^2 + rR) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)} \cdot \cos(90^\circ + \alpha)$$

Simplification leads to:

$$2(r^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos(180^\circ - \alpha - \beta))$$

$$= 2 \cdot (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) - 2R \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)} \cdot \cos(90^\circ + \alpha)$$

With the relations $\cos(180^\circ - \alpha - \beta) = -\cos(\alpha + \beta)$ and $\cos(90^\circ + \alpha) = -\sin \alpha$ we obtain:

$$(r^2 + rR) \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) - (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) = R \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)} \cdot \sin \alpha$$

Squared:

$$(r^2 + rR)^2 \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 + (R^2 + Rr)^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)^2$$

$$- 2 \cdot (r^2 + rR) \cdot (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)$$

$$= 2R^2 \cdot (R^2 + Rr) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot \sin^2 \alpha$$

Simplified:

$$(r^4 + 2Rr^3 + r^2R^2) \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 + (R^4 + 2rR^3 + R^2r^2) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)^2$$

$$- 2 \cdot (2R^2r^2 + r^3R + rR^3) \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)$$

$$= (2R^4 + 2rR^3) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot \sin^2 \alpha$$

Ordered to powers:

$$(1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 r^4 + (2R \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)))^2 - 2R \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot r^3$$

$$+ (R^2 \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 + R^2 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)^2 - 4R^2 \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)) \cdot r^2$$

$$+ (2R^3 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)^2 - 2R^3 \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) - 2R^3 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot \sin^2 \alpha) \cdot r$$

3

$$+R^4 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)^2 - 2R^4 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot \sin^2 \alpha = 0$$

Finally:

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 \cdot r^4 + 2R \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos \beta) \cdot r^3 \\ & + R^2 \cdot ((1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2 + (1 - \cos \beta)^2 - 4 \cdot (1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)) \cdot r^2 \\ & + 2R^3 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot (-\cos \beta - \cos(\alpha + \beta) - \sin^2 \alpha) \cdot r \\ & + R^4 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta - 2 \sin^2 \alpha) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have a polynomial of degree 4 for r . The further calculation is done with Bronstein [2] (chapter 2.4.2.3 p.131,133) and "DTV Atlas zur Mathematik" [3] (chapter "Anwendungen der Galoistheorie I" p.110). We transform to a normed polynomial:

$$r^4 + ar^3 + br^2 + cr + d = 0$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \frac{2R \cdot (\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos \beta)}{1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)} \\ b &= R^2 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{(1 - \cos \beta)^2}{(1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2} - \frac{4 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)}{1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta)} \right) \\ c &= \frac{-2R^3 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot (\cos \beta + \cos(\alpha + \beta) + \sin^2 \alpha)}{(1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2} \\ d &= \frac{R^4 \cdot (1 - \cos \beta) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta - 2 \sin^2 \alpha)}{(1 + \cos(\alpha + \beta))^2} \end{aligned}$$

The normed polynomial can be reduced to following polynomial:

$$z^4 + pz^2 + qz + \bar{r} = 0$$

with $r = z - \frac{a}{4}$ and coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} p &= b - \frac{3}{8} \cdot a^2 & q &= c - \frac{ab}{2} + \frac{a^3}{8} \\ \bar{r} &= d - \frac{ac}{4} + \frac{1}{16} \cdot a^2 b - \frac{3}{256} \cdot a^4 \end{aligned}$$

Now we need the resolvent cubic:

$$y^3 + 2py^2 + (p^2 - 4\bar{r}) \cdot y - q^2 = 0$$

4

Then we view the reduced term:

$$\bar{y}^3 + \bar{p}\bar{y} + \bar{q} = 0$$

This polynomial can be determined from a general polynomial of degree 3. For the reduction formulas see Bronstein [2] (chapter 2.4.2.3 p.131) and "DTV Atlas zur Mathematik" [3] (p. 110). We obtain with these reduction formulas used to the resolvent cubic:

$$\bar{p} = \frac{3 \cdot (p^2 - 4\bar{r}) - 4p^2}{3}$$

$$\bar{q} = \frac{2 \cdot (2p)^3}{27} - \frac{2p \cdot (p^2 - 4\bar{r})}{3} - q^2$$

We can solve the reduced polynomial with Cardan's solution of the cubic:

$$D = \left(\frac{\bar{p}}{3}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{\bar{q}}{2}\right)^2$$

$$u = \sqrt[3]{-\frac{\bar{q}}{2} + \sqrt{D}} \quad v = -\frac{\bar{p}}{3u}$$

The solution of the reduced polynomial can be written:

$$\bar{y}_1 = u + v$$

$$\bar{y}_2 = -\frac{u+v}{2} + \frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3} \quad i = \sqrt{-1}$$

$$\bar{y}_3 = -\frac{u+v}{2} - \frac{u-v}{2} \cdot i\sqrt{3}$$

The solutions $\bar{y}_1, \bar{y}_2$ and $\bar{y}_3$ can be real or complex. With these solutions we can calculate the solutions

$$y_i = \bar{y}_i - \frac{2p}{3} \quad i \in 1, 2, 3$$

of the resolvent cubic. Next we determine the solution of the reduced polynomial with degree 4:

$$z_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\sqrt{y_1} + \sqrt{y_2} - \sqrt{y_3})$$

$$z_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\sqrt{y_1} - \sqrt{y_2} + \sqrt{y_3})$$

$$z_3 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-\sqrt{y_1} + \sqrt{y_2} + \sqrt{y_3})$$

$$z_4 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-\sqrt{y_1} - \sqrt{y_2} - \sqrt{y_3})$$

Besides the condition $\sqrt{y_1} \cdot \sqrt{y_2} \cdot \sqrt{y_3} = q$ must be valid. The solutions can be real or complex numbers. Finally we get the solution of the polynomial of origin with:

$$r_i = z_i - \frac{a}{4} \quad i \in 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Only the real z_i are interesting for our problem. Possible at most are 4 real solutions for r . The positive real solutions for r can be inserted in:

$$x = +\sqrt{2 \cdot (R^2 + rR) \cdot (1 - \cos \beta)}$$

Then we obtain solutions for x . The values (r, x) can be checked with the equations (1) and (2). 4 solutions at most are possible.

Bibliography

- [1] Hans-Jochen Bartsch "Taschenbuch mathematischer Formeln"
7.-9.edition 1986 VEB Fachbuchverlag Leipsic
- [2] I.N. Bronstein, K.A. Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik"
Teubner Verlagsgesellschaft Leipsic 1985 22.edition
- [3] DTV Atlas zur Mathematik Band 1 3.edition 1978 DTV Verlag Munich
- [4] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases
well solved" Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag
Berlin, 2001